

Northern Ireland Good Friday Agreement

Date Signed: 10 April, 1998

Accord Type: Comprehensive Peace Agreement

Country: United Kingdom

95.24

Implementation Score after 10 years

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PROVISIONS IN THIS ACCORD

Cease Fire
Powersharing Transitional Government
Constitutional Reform
Inter-ethnic/State Relations
Electoral/Political Party Reform
Decentralization/Federalism
Dispute Resolution Committee
Judiciary Reform
Police Reform
Demobilization
Disarmament
Reintegration
Prisoner Release
Paramilitary Groups
Human Rights
Right of Self-Determination
Citizenship Reform
Women's Rights
Education Reform
Official Language and Symbol
Minority Rights
Reparations
Economic and Social Development
Ratification Mechanism
Detailed Implementation Timeline
Independence Referendum
Review of Agreement
Verification/Monitoring Mechanism

Inter-ethnic/State Relations

Implementation Timeline

About this Provision

Strand One: Democratic Institutions in Northern Ireland

Safeguards

5. There will be safeguards to ensure that all sections of the community can participate and work together successfully in the operation of these institutions and that all sections of the community are protected, including:

(a) allocations of Committee Chairs, Ministers and Committee membership in proportion to party strengths;

(b) the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and any Bill of Rights for Northern Ireland supplementing it, which neither the Assembly nor public bodies can infringe, together with a Human Rights Commission;

(c) arrangements to provide that key decisions and legislation are proofed to ensure that they do not infringe the ECHR and any Bill of Rights for Northern Ireland;

(d) arrangements to ensure key decisions are taken on a cross-community basis;

(i) either parallel consent, i.e. a majority of those members present and voting, including a majority of the unionist and nationalist designations present and voting;

(ii) or a weighted majority (60%) of members present and voting, including at least 40% of each of the nationalist and unionist designations present and voting.

Key decisions requiring cross-community support will be designated in advance, including election of the Chair of the Assembly, the First Minister and Deputy First Minister, standing orders and budget allocations. In other cases such decisions could be triggered by a petition

of concern brought by a significant minority of Assembly members (30/108).

(e) an Equality Commission to monitor a statutory obligation to promote equality of opportunity in specified areas and parity of esteem between the two main communities, and to investigate individual complaints against public bodies.

Executive Authority

14. Executive authority to be discharged on behalf of the Assembly by a First Minister and Deputy First Minister and up to ten Ministers with Departmental responsibilities.

15. The First Minister and Deputy First Minister shall be jointly elected into office by the Assembly voting on a cross-community basis, according to 5(d)(i) above.

16. Following the election of the First Minister and Deputy First Minister, the posts of Ministers will be allocated to parties on the basis of the d'á€™Hondt system by reference to the number of seats each party has in the Assembly.

Legislation

(b) decisions by simple majority of members voting, except when decision on a cross-community basis is required;

Relations with other institutions

34. A consultative Civic Forum will be established. It will comprise representatives of the business, trade union and voluntary sectors, and such other sectors as agreed by the First Minister and the Deputy First Minister. It will act as a consultative mechanism on social, economic and cultural issues. The First Minister and the Deputy First Minister will by

agreement provide administrative support for the Civic Forum and establish guidelines for the selection of representatives to the Civic Forum.

(Note: Along with safeguards and relations with other institutions designed to promote cross-community relationships, the Good Friday Agreement also provided for the establishment of North/South Ministerial Council to promote relationships between the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland.)

Please always cite: ["Annualized implementation data on comprehensive intrastate peace accords, 1989–2012."](#) Madhav Joshi, Jason Michael Quinn, and Patrick M. Regan. *Journal of Peace Research* 52 (2015): 551-562.

